

25 YEARS

Joint Monitoring Migratory Birds in the Wadden Sea

Trends of Migratory and Wintering Waterbirds in the Wadden Sea 1987/1988-2011/2012

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Progress Report

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Progress Report
Trends of Migratory and Wintering
Waterbirds in the Wadden Sea
1987/1988 - 2011/2012

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Monitoring migratory and wintering birds, the JMMB program

The Wadden Sea constitutes one of the world's most important wetlands for migratory waterbirds. It is the single most important staging and moulting area and an important wintering area for waterbirds on the East Atlantic Flyway from the Arctic to South Africa. The Joint Monitoring of Migratory Birds (JMMB) program is carried out in the framework of the Trilateral Monitoring and Assessment Program (TMAP), and constitutes an internationally coordinated long-term monitoring program. It covers a large connected ecoregion stretching from Den Helder in The Netherlands to Esbjerg in Denmark; regular ground counts for most species and areas plus aerial counts for sea ducks involves hundreds of observers and several institutes and agencies.

After the publication of trends, comprehensive species accounts and assessments in the most recent reports (Blew *et al.* 2005 and Blew *et al.* 2007), the JMMB group agreed, that from now on a yearly update of these trend calculation shall be published on this website. Here, trends of 34 waterbird species for the international Wadden Sea and the four regions - The

Netherlands, the Federal States of Germany, Niedersachsen and Schleswig-Holstein, and Denmark will be presented.

Details of the "Joint Monitoring program of Migratory Birds in the Wadden Sea" are given in Rösner *et al.*, (1993) and updated in Blew *et al.*, (2005). This program, consisting of international synchronous counts, spring-tide counts and aerial counts (only Common Eider), has been carried out by all Wadden Sea countries since 1992. Some differences between the countries' programs exist, due to different national approaches and older already existing counting programs, but these do not hamper the overall goal for calculating trends. Because many usable counting data before 1992 exist as well, it has been decided to include counts back to the season 1987/1988.

The area considered is the Wadden Sea Cooperation Area. This is, in general terms, the area seaward of the main dike (or, where the main dike is absent, the spring-high-tide-water line, and in the rivers, the brackish-water limit) up to 3 nautical miles from the baseline or the offshore boundaries of the Conservation Area (Essink *et al.*, 2005). The total area covers 14,700 km², with 4,534 km² of tidal flats.

Drawing:
Niels Knudsen

2 Data and methods

Data used in the analyses are a mixture of total counts (two internationally, up to five nationally) and counts of a selection of sites which are counted more frequently (12–25 times a season). At present a total of 594 counting units are defined in the Wadden Sea, which are included in the analyses. For this report, the original counting data, available at the smallest level have been used.

Trends are calculated and presented for 34 waterbird species. These are species which use the Wadden Sea during stop-over on migration or as a wintering area with large parts of their flyway population. For 10 different subspecies of 5 of these 34 species trends are calculated also, since the subspecies can be separated by different periods of their presence in the Wadden Sea area during the year. Trends for subspecies are calculated for Common Ringed-Plover, Red Knot, Bar-tailed Godwit, Redbank and Turnstone. Species which only occur in low numbers or species which cannot be counted with sufficient representativeness have been excluded from the analyses (for a more detailed explanation see Rösner et al., 1994).

Despite a large dataset with lots of real count data available also missing counts are present. A complete dataset involves counts for all counting units in all months of the year. To analyse the waterbird count data, UINDEX (Bell, 1995) was used to account for missing counts in the dataset, and then TrendSpotter is applied to calcu-

late trends (Visser, 2004, Soldaat et al 2007). The program UINDEX is estimating bird numbers for missing counts (imputing) taking into account site-, year- and month-factors (Underhill & Prys-Jones 1994). Sites are grouped in four regional strata representing the four different Wadden Sea "countries". The counted and imputed values for each month are added to yearly averages for the respective "bird-years", covering the period from July to June of the following year (Fig. 2.1). After that with the program TrendSpotter so-called "flexible trends" are calculated. These are particularly suitable for time series data with different periods of decreasing, stable or increasing trends (Visser 2004, Soldaat et al., 2007). A trend line calculated by TrendSpotter hardly deviates from a moving average or a smoothed trend line as calculated by a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) (e.g. Atkinson et al., 2006). TrendSpotter calculates also confidence intervals and differences between the trend level of the last year and each of the preceding years can be assessed (Soldaat et al. 2007). This way trend estimates can be given for any period, as for example the last 10 years and the whole time period, as in the current analyses.

Trend estimates given within the text are used as categories (Fig. 2.2).

This progress report presents data of the period 1987/1988 - 2011/2012 except from Niedersachsen where data was available only up to 2010/2011.

Figure 2.1 Example of the treatment of data for the trend analyses. First the seasonal pattern is reconstructed by using counted numbers and imputed numbers for each month for a certain species (left graph of the figure, dark blue is counted, light blue is imputed). Then the average over all months is taken and this is the 'yearly estimate' to be used in the trend analyses (right graph). The trend line and confidence limits are calculated over all year estimates.

Figure 2.2 Trend classification used to express annual changes in waterbird numbers. Dots represent trend values, horizontal lines their 95% confidence limits.

Acknowledgements

In Denmark the counts were carried out by the National Environmental Research Institute (NERI, University of Aarhus). Aerial counts were carried out by NERI up to 1992, and during the years after they were organized through a collaboration between NERI and Ribe Environmental Center, Ministry of the Environment.

In Schleswig-Holstein the monitoring was initiated by the Ornithological Society Schleswig-Holstein (OAG SH) in the 1960s; regular monitoring was jointly organized by the OAG SH and the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) in 1987 and during the first period until 1994 funded by the federal state Schleswig-Holstein and the Federal Ministry of Environment (Federal Environment Agency) as part of an ecosystem research project. Since then it was funded by the National Park Administration Schleswig-Holstein Wadden Sea. The coordination of the project moved from WWF to the Schutzstation Wattenmeer e.V. in 2004. The aerial surveys of Common Eider

and Shelduck were separately financed by the National Park Administration Schleswig-Holstein Wadden Sea.

In Niedersachsen and the Hamburg regions the counts were organized by the Bird Conservation Station in the Lower Saxony Water Management, Coastal Defence and Nature Conservation Agency (NLWKN), formerly Lower Saxony Agency for Ecology (NLÖ). The aerial surveys of Common Eider were financed by the Lower Saxony Wadden Sea National Park Authority.

The waterbird counts in the Dutch Wadden Sea are part of the national monitoring program of waterbirds in The Netherlands, which is a cooperation between the Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, the Ministry of Water Management and Public Works, Statistics The Netherlands (CBS), Vogelbescherming Nederland and SOVON Dutch Centre for Field Ornithology. The aerial surveys of Common Eider were carried out under the responsibility of the Ministry of Water Management and Public Works.

Photo:
Bo Lassen Christiansen

3 Overview trends

Table 3.1
Trends until 2011/2012 - The whole 25 and last 10 years time period. Data for Nds/HH was only available up to 2010/2011. The species names in the table are sorted according to the Euring Code.

Species	Long-term 25-years trend 1987/1988 - 2011/2012					Short-term 10-year trend 2000/2001 - 2011/2012				
	WS	DK	SH	Nds/ HH*	NL	WS	DK	SH	Nds/ HH*	NL
Great Cormorant	↑↑	↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑	↓	↓↓↓	↑	→	↓
Eurasian Spoonbill	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑	↑↑
Barnacle Goose	↑↑	↑↑	↑	↑	↑↑	↑	↑	↑	—	↑
Brent Goose	↓	↓↓↓	↓	↓	→	↓	↓↓↓	→	↓	→
Common Shelduck	↓	—	↓	↓	↑	→	—	↓	→	↑
Eurasian Wigeon	→	→	↓	↑	↓	↓	→	↓	→	↓
Common Teal	→	→	→	↓	→	—	—	→	—	—
Mallard	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	↓	↓
Northern Pintail	↑	—	→	→	↑	—	—	↑	—	→
Northern Shoveler	→	↑	↑	→	→	→	—	↑	→	→
Common Eider	no long term trend available - counts started only 1993					↓	↓	—	↓	→
Eurasian Oystercatcher	↓	→	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Pied Avocet	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	↓	↓	→	↓	→
Great Ringed Plover	↑	—	↑	↓	↑	↑	—	↑	—	↑
Kentish Plover	↓	—	↓	↓↓↓	↓	↓	—	↓	↓↓↓	↓
European Golden Plover	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	↓	↓	→	↓	→
Grey Plover	→	↑	↓	↓	↑	↓	→	↓	↓	→
Northern Lapwing	→	→	↑	→	↑	→	→	—	→	↑
Red Knot	↓	—	↓	→	→	→	—	↓	—	—
Sanderling	↑	↑	→	→	↑↑	↑	↑	→	→	↑
Curlew Sandpiper	→	—	—	↓↓↓	↑	—	↓	—	↓↓↓	—
Dunlin	↓	↓	↓	→	↑	↓	↓	↓	→	↑
Ruff	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	↓	↓	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	↓↓↓	—	↓
Bar-tailed Godwit	→	↓	↓	→	↑	→	↓	↓	→	→
Whimbrel	→	↓↓↓	↑	↓	↑	→	↓↓↓	—	↓	—
Eurasian Curlew	→	↑↑	↓	→	↑	→	—	↓	→	→
Spotted Redshank	↓	→	↓	→	↓	↓	→	↓	→	↓
Common Redshank	→	→	↓	↓	↑	→	—	↓	→	↑
Common Greenshank	→	→	↓	→	↑	→	—	↓	→	→
Ruddy Turnstone	→	↓	→	↑	→	→	↓↓↓	↓	↑	→
Black-headed Gull	↓	↓	→	↓	→	→	↓	↑	↓	→
Common Gull	→	↓	↓	→	↑	→	↓	→	—	→
European Herring Gull	↓	→	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	↓	↓	↓
Great Black-backed Gull	↓	↓	↓	↓	→	→	↓↓↓	↓	↓	→

* Data for Niedersachsen/Hamburg was only available up to 2010/2011.

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

WS - Wadden Sea; DK - Denmark; SH - Schleswig-Holstein; Nds/HH - Niedersachsen/Hamburg; NL - The Netherlands

Figure 3.1
Trend categories for the 25-year period for the International Wadden Sea and the four countries, calculated with TrendSpotter on yearly estimates, ranked after trend category and value.

Figure 3.2
Trend categories for the 10-year period for the International Wadden Sea and the four countries, calculated with TrendSpotter on yearly estimates, ranked after trend category and value.

Figure 3.3
Proportion of flyway population with regard to estimated numbers (Wetlands International 2013).

Drawing:
Gundolf Reichert

In order to help to identify possible relationships between the species' trends and their ecological traits, trends of single species were combined. Each bird species has been allocated to each of four different guilds, namely food, feeding habitat, breeding and wintering grounds.

The decisions for these allocations have not been clear-cut in all cases; in particular regarding food or feeding habitat, the choice was to pick those which represented the main food or feeding habitat, respectively.

For the combined indices the geometrical mean of species-specific indices have been used.

Feeding Habitat

Species utilizing beaches or tidal areas are stable, and those using the salt marshes have been stable, but are declining during the recent 10 years; the species of the coastal grasslands (European Golden Plover, Northern Lapwing, Ruff) are all on the decline.

Breeding Range

Trends are stable for the arctic breeders and decreasing for the non-arctic breeders.

Wintering Range

Trends are decreasing for those species wintering in Europe, while those wintering in Africa are even increasing.

Results

Food

Species depending on fish show a positive development, while those feeding more or less opportunistically on "other invertebrates" are stable. The herbivorous species seem to decline now after a stable period up to 2000, species feeding on worms or shellfish are on the decline. The only omnivorous species, Greater Black-backed Gull, is also declining.

Figure 3.4 Combined trends according to food guilds, feeding habitat, breeding range and wintering range (see Table A1.1 & A1.2, p62-63). Trends were aggregated by using the geometrical mean of single species within each category.

4 Species accounts

Photo:
Gerold Lürßen

4.1 Great Cormorant

Phalacrocorax carbo

00720

DK: Skarv

D: Kormoran

NL: Aalscholver

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.1.1-4.1.6 Trends of Great Cormorant in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Great Cormorant numbers show a remarkable increase in the Wadden Sea from the 1980s up to 2003 during all seasons, reflecting the increase in the breeding populations in Northern Europe. This long-term increase has recently turned into a sustained decrease most visible in the Netherlands and Denmark; lately, these negative trends are also indicated in Schleswig-Holstein and Niedersachsen/Hamburg, while the long-term trend is still an increase.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Great Cormorant in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	↓↓
(C) Denmark		↑	↓↓↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑↑	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑↑	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↓↓

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.1.7 Absolute numbers of Great Cormorant in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.2 Eurasian Spoonbill

01440

Platalea leucorodia

DK: Skestork

D: Löffler

NL: Lepelaar

Figure 4.2.1.4.2.6 Trends of Eurasian Spoonbill in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

The Wadden Sea is near the northern border of the Eurasian Spoonbill breeding range, but numbers increase up to now especially in the Netherlands, but also in Niedersachsen/Hamburg and Schleswig-Holstein. The non-breeding numbers reflect the breeding population and numbers are increasing in all parts of the Wadden Sea.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Eurasian Spoonbill in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.2.7 Absolute numbers of Eurasian Spoonbill in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	↑↑
(C) Denmark		↑↑	↑↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑↑	↑↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑↑	↑↑
(F) The Netherlands		↑↑	↑↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable ■ uncertain

4.3 Barnacle Goose

Branta leucopsis

01670

DK: Bramgå

D: Weißwangengans

NL: Brandgans

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.3.1-4.3.6 Trends of Barnacle Goose in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by TrendSpotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

The Barnacle Goose flyway population is increasing, and this trend is also reflected clearly by the numbers in the Wadden Sea. Though fluctuations occur in Niedersachsen/Hamburg and the Netherlands, the short-term trend estimate is stable. During the last 10 years the species has prolonged its staging period in spring and its departure has moved into May.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Barnacle Goose in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑↑	↑
(C) Denmark		↑↑	↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑↑	↑

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.3.7 Absolute numbers of Barnacle Goose in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.4 Dark-bellied Brent Goose

01680

Branta bernicla bernicla

DK: Mørkbuget Knortegås D: Dunkelbäuchige Ringelgans NL: Rotgans

Figure 4.4.1–4.4.6 Trends of Dark-bellied Brent Goose in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

The Dark-bellied Brent Goose population has increased until the mid 1990s and decreased afterwards. Due to those fluctuations, the overall trends in the Wadden Sea appear to be stable, which also applies for the Netherlands and Niedersachsen/Niedersachsen. Within the fluctuations, both Denmark and Schleswig-Holstein show decreasing trends.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Dark-bellied Brent Goose in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.4.7 Absolute numbers of Dark-bellied Brent Goose in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002–2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 – 2011/12	2002/03 – 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓↓	↓↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.5 Common Shelduck

Tadorna tadorna

01730

DK: Gravand

D: Brandgans

NL: Bergeend

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.5.1-4.5.6 Trends of Common Shelduck in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Some 80% of the Common Shelduck flyway population can be found in the Wadden Sea. Overall numbers – counted from the ground throughout the year – decreased up to the mid 1990’s and seemed to level off. However, due to a continuous slight decrease after 2000, the long-term Wadden Sea trend is decreasing, the 10-year trend still stable. Decreases occur both in Schleswig-Holstein and Niedersachsen/Hamburg, while trends in Denmark and the Netherlands are stable, fluctuating or slightly increasing.

The Shelduck moulting population, with its main concentration in the Schleswig-Holstein Wadden Sea, has been increasing up to 2000, but is continuously decreasing thereafter. The long-term trend is now stable, but the short-term trend clearly decreasing.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Shelduck in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.5.7 Absolute numbers of Common Shelduck in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.6 Eurasian Wigeon

01790

Anas penelope

DK: Pibeand

D: Pfeifente

NL: Smient

Figure 4.6.1-4.6.6 Trends of Eurasian Wigeon in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

The trend of the Eurasian Wigeon has seen increasing numbers up to the mid 1990s; following two cold winters in 1996 and 1997 numbers decreased, but stabilized for a while thereafter. Now the long term overall Wadden Sea trend is stable, but the short term trend is decreasing. Decreasing trends are found in the Netherlands and now also in Schleswig-Holstein. Denmark shows stable trends.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Eurasian Wigeon in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.6.7 Absolute numbers of Eurasian Wigeon in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	↓
(C) Denmark		→	→
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑	→
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.7 Common Teal

Anas crecca

01840

DK: Krikand

D: Krickente

NL: Wintertaling

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.7.1-4.7.6 Trends of Common Teal in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by TrendSpotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Despite an increasing flyway population, the Common Teal numbers in the Wadden Sea show stable numbers during the long-term trends; short-term trends are uncertain. Large fluctuations do not allow for short-term trends in the most regions. Since Teal numbers in the Wadden Sea only represent 10% of the flyway population, trends in the Wadden Sea depend more on climate and habitat availability than on flyway trends.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Teal in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	—
(C) Denmark		→	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		→	—

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.7.7 Absolute numbers of Common Teal in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.8 Mallard

01860

Anas platyrhynchos

DK: Gråand

D: Stockente

NL: Wilde Eend

Figure 4.8.1-4.8.6 Trends of Mallard in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95% confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

The Mallard occurs in the Wadden Sea only with less than 5% of its flyway populations. The overall trends are moderate but long-lasting decreases in the entire Wadden Sea; while the northern region trends (DK, SH) stabilized, yet with large fluctuations, the southern regions show continuing decreases.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Mallard in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.8.7 Absolute numbers of Mallard in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↗
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease ↔ stable — uncertain

4.9 Northern Pintail

Anas acuta

01890

DK: Spidsand

D: Spießente

NL: Pijlstaart

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.9.1-4.9.6 Trends of Northern Pintail in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by TrendSpotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

While the Northern Pintail flyway population trend is stable, the developments in the Wadden Sea, however, holding up to 50% of the flyway population, show large fluctuations. Where data allow a trend to be calculated, its mostly stable or increasing.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Northern Pintail in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑	—
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.9.7 Absolute numbers of Northern Pintail in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.10 Northern Shoveler

01940

Anas clypeata

DK: Skeand

D: Löffelente

NL: Slobeend

Figure 4.10.1–4.10.6 Trends of Northern Shoveler in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

The numbers of Northern Shoveler using the Wadden Sea represent some 20% of the flyway population. The overall Wadden Sea trend is stable, including slight increases in Denmark and Schleswig-Holstein, and an apparent stable situation in Niedersachsen/Hamburg and in the Netherlands.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Northern Shoveler in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.10.7 Absolute numbers of Northern Shoveler in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002–2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 – 2011/12	2002/03 – 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↑	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.11 Common Eider

Somateria mollissima

02060

DK: Ederfugl

D: Eiderente

NL: Eidereend

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.11.1–4.11.6 Trends of Common Eider in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by TrendSpotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Common Eider numbers counted from the airplane at mid winter (only since 1993) were stable in the Wadden Sea only for the first years up to 1995/1996 and continuously decreased thereafter. This decrease also applies for the 10-year trends in Niedersachsen/Hamburg and Denmark, while numbers in the Netherlands are stable and in Schleswig-Holstein fluctuating.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Eider in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1992/1993 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	no long term trend available - counts started in 1993	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea			↓
(C) Denmark			↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein			—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg			↓
(F) The Netherlands			↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.11.7 Absolute numbers of Common Eider in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002–2011/2012. Numbers are derived by aerial counts.

4.12 Eurasian Oystercatcher

04500

Haematopus ostralegus

DK: Strandskade

D: Austernfischer

NL: Scholekster

Figure 4.12.1-4.12.6 Trends of Eurasian Oystercatcher in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Up to 50% of the Eurasian Oystercatcher flyway population can be counted in the Wadden Sea. Overall Wadden Sea numbers show a striking regular and long-lasting decrease also in all regions.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Eurasian Oystercatcher in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.12.7 Absolute numbers of Eurasian Oystercatcher in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↔	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease ↔ stable — uncertain

4.13 Pied Avocet

Recurvirostra avocetta

04560

DK: Klyde

D: Säbelschnäbler

NL: Kluut

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.13.1-4.13.6 Trends of Pied Avocet in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Peak numbers of Pied Avocet occur during autumn, when more than 50% of its flyway population can be found in the Wadden Sea. The trend for the flyway population is stable, however, the overall trend in the Wadden Sea is a moderate but continuous decrease, even though results since 1995 seem to be rather levelled. The decrease is also visible in all regions but the Netherlands, where the trends are stable.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Pied Avocet in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↗ moderate increase
↘ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.13.7 Absolute numbers of Pied Avocet in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.14 Common Ringed Plover

04700

Charadrius hiaticula

DK: Stor Præstekrave D: Sandregenpfeifer NL: Bontbekplevier

Figure 4.14.1-4.14.6 Trends of Common Ringed Plover in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Three populations of Common Ringed Plover pass the Wadden Sea during migration, *C. h. hiaticula* being present from October to April, but large numbers of both the arctic breeding *C. h. tundrae* and *C. h. psammodroma* coming through during May. Some results are fluctuating, but show a moderate increase for the entire Wadden Sea and the Netherlands. Numbers in Niedersachsen/Hamburg are decreasing overall, fluctuating in Denmark.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Ringed Plover in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.14.7 Absolute numbers of Common Ringed Plover in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑	↑
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.15 Kentish Plover

Charadrius alexandrinus

04770

DK: Hvidbrystet Præstekrave D: Seeregenpfeifer NL: Strandplevier

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.15.1-4.15.6 Trends of Kentish Plover in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

For the Kentish Plover, the Wadden Sea holds less than 1% of the entire flyway population, and overall very low numbers are registered during the synchronous counts. Both during spring and autumn these birds represent the local breeding population. The trend in the overall Wadden Sea and most of its regions is decreasing both in the long- and short-term.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Kentish Plover in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓↓	↓↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↕ moderate increase
↕ moderate decrease
 ↔ stable
 — uncertain

Figure 4.15.7 Absolute numbers of Kentish Plover in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.16 European Golden Plover

04850

Pluvialis apricaria

DK: Hjejle

D: Goldregenpfeifer

NL: Goudplevier

Figure 4.16.1–4.16.6 Trends of European Golden Plover in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Of the European Golden Plover, three sub-populations may occur in the Wadden Sea, with the largest share belonging to the sub-population *P. a. altifrons*, which breeds in Northern Europe and winters in Central and Western Europe and North-West Africa. Only a small part of that population is covered by the coordinated counts in the Wadden Sea as most birds roost on fields and meadows further inland. The overall trend in the Wadden Sea and its regions is decreasing in both the long- and the short-term trends; only in the Netherlands, the long-term trend is still stable.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for European Golden Plover in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.16.7 Absolute numbers of European Golden Plover in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002–2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 – 2011/12	2002/03 – 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↗
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↗	↗

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↗ moderate increase
↘ moderate decrease ↔ stable — uncertain

4.17 Grey Plover

Pluvialis squatarola

04860

DK: Strandhjejle D: Kiebitzregenpfeifer NL: Zilverplevier

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.17.1-4.17.6 Trends of Grey Plover in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

More than 50% of the total flyway population of Grey Plover uses the Wadden Sea outside the breeding season, thus this region is of high importance for the species. The total flyway population is decreasing, but in the Wadden Sea the overall trend is stable during the long but decreasing during the short term trend. Long-term trend increases are still registered in the Netherlands and Denmark, while decreases occur in Niedersachsen/Hamburg and Schleswig-Holstein.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Grey Plover in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	↓
(C) Denmark		↑	→
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↑	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.17.7 Absolute numbers of Grey Plover in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.18 Northern Lapwing

04930

Vanellus vanellus

DK: Vibe

D: Kiebitz

NL: Kievit

Figure 4.18.1-4.18.6 Trends of Northern Lapwing in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Only a small fraction of the decreasing Northern Lapwing flyway population uses the Wadden Sea. Registered numbers show considerable fluctuations, but the overall Wadden Sea trends are stable.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Northern Lapwing in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.18.7 Absolute numbers of Northern Lapwing in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		→	→
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.19 Red Knot

Calidris canutus

04960

DK: Islandsk Ryle

D: Knutt

NL: Kanoetstrandloper

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.19.1-4.19.6 Trends of Red Knot in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95% confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Large parts of both flyway populations of the Red Knot, the *C. c. canutus* migrating from Africa to Siberia and the *C. c. islandica* wintering in the European regions and breeding in Greenland and Canada, use the Wadden Sea. While the overall long-term trend in the Wadden Sea is decreasing, the short-term trend is stable. Continuous decreases occur in Schleswig-Holstein, while numbers in most other regions are fluctuating and show no clear trend direction.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Red Knot in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	—
(F) The Netherlands		→	—

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.19.7 Absolute numbers of Red Knot in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.20 Sanderling

04970

Calidris alba

DK: Sandløber

D: Sanderling

NL: Drietenstrandloper

Figure 4.20.1-4.20.6 Trends of Sanderling in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Sanderling numbers are difficult to survey due to high peak numbers during a short time period in spring; if the counts do not occur within this time window the numbers can vary greatly from year to year. The overall trends in the Wadden Sea are increasing, mostly on account of results in the Netherlands and Denmark. Trends are stable in Schleswig-Holstein and Niedersachsen/Hamburg.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Sanderling in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.20.7 Absolute numbers of Sanderling in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑	↑
(C) Denmark		↑	↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable ■ uncertain

4.21 Curlew Sandpiper

Calidris ferruginea

05090

DK: Krumnæbbet Ryle D: Sichelstrandläufer NL: Krombekstrandloper

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.21.1-4.21.6 Trends of Curlew Sandpiper in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

The Curlew Sandpiper has a large flyway population of which only 1-2% visit the Wadden Sea in a very short period during July/August in a small number of sites, with the majority covered in Schleswig-Holstein, but low numbers in Denmark. The flyway population is increasing. Due to large fluctuations in counting results, most trend estimates in the Wadden Sea and its regions are fluctuating, however, Niedersachsen/Hamburg comes out with decreasing trends.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Curlew Sandpiper in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	—
(C) Denmark		—	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		—	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓↓	↓↓
(F) The Netherlands		↑	—

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

Figure 4.21.7 Absolute numbers of Curlew Sandpiper in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.22 Dunlin

05120

Calidris alpina

DK: Almindelig Ryle D: Alpenstrandläufer NL: Bonte Strandloper

Figure 4.22.1-4.22.6 Trends of Dunlin in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

While the trends for the flyway populations of the two sub-species of Dunlin (*C.c. alpina* and *C.c. schinzii*) are stable, the overall long- and short-term trends in the Wadden Sea, where large numbers and most likely large proportions of these flyway populations are present during the yearly cycle, show moderate decreases. Most notable are decreases in the Northern region (Denmark, Schleswig-Holstein), and opposite to these increases in the Netherlands; stable but fluctuating numbers seem to apply for Niedersachsen/Hamburg.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Dunlin in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.22.7 Absolute numbers of Dunlin in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↔	↔
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease ↔ stable — uncertain

4.23 Ruff

Philomachus pugnax

05170

DK: Brushane

D: Kampfläufer

NL: Kemphaan

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.23.1-4.23.6 Trends of Ruff in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95% confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Less than 1% of the Ruff flyway population migrates through the Wadden Sea, where both the long- and short-term trends are moderately to strongly decreasing in most regions. The species presence depends on feeding possibilities and weather, thus numbers are highly variable from year to year.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Ruff in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓↓↓	↓↓↓
(C) Denmark		↓↓↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓↓↓	↓↓↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.23.7 Absolute numbers of Ruff in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.24 Bar-tailed Godwit

05340

Limosa lapponica

DK: Lille Kobbersneppe D: Pfuhschnepfe NL: Rosse Grutto

Figure 4.24.1-4.24.6 Trends of Bar-tailed Godwit in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Two populations of the Bar-tailed Godwit migrate through the Wadden Sea; the nominate sub-species *L. l. lapponica* breeds in high arctic Scandinavia and Northern Russia, and winters in coastal Western Europe and North-West Africa, and thus is present in the Wadden Sea most of the year from September to April. The *L. l. taymyrensis* breeds in Western and Central Siberia and winters in coastal West and South-West Africa; individuals of this population will migrate through the Wadden Sea in May and returning during July and August. Overall numbers in the Wadden Sea are stable. Yet, most remarkably is the contrast of an increase in the Netherlands and decreases in Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark; numbers in Niedersachsen/Hamburg are stable.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Bar-tailed Godwit in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.24.7 Absolute numbers of Bar-tailed Godwit in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable ■ uncertain

4.25 Whimbrel

Numenius phaeopus

05380

DK: Lille Regnspove D: Regenbrachvogel NL: Regenwulp

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.25.1-4.25.6 Trends of Whimbrel in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95% confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Only 1-2% of the Whimbrel flyway population is counted in the Wadden Sea region. Long- and short-term trends are decreasing in the Wadden Sea, and also in Denmark and Niedersachsen/Hamburg. We see a stable situation in Schleswig-Holstein and the Netherlands. It must be noted, that overall very low numbers, large fluctuations and single exceptional counts do not allow a clear assessment.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Whimbrel in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↓ ↓	↓ ↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	—
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↑	—

↑ strong increase
 ↓ ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

Figure 4.25.7 Absolute numbers of Whimbrel in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.26 Eurasian Curlew

05410

Numenius arquata

DK: Stor Regnspove

D: Großer Brachvogel

NL: Wulp

Figure 4.26.1-4.26.6 Trends of Eurasian Curlew in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

The Eurasian Curlew flyway population is decreasing. However, the Wadden Sea population, representing some 35-40% of the flyway population, is stable both in the long- and short-term trends. This includes strong increases in Denmark and moderate increases in the Netherlands, while Schleswig-Holstein shows long- and short-term decreases. In Niedersachsen/Hamburg the trend is stable.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Eurasian Curlew in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.26.7 Absolute numbers of Eurasian Curlew in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↑↑	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓↓	↓↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	→

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.27 Spotted Redshank

Tringa erythropus

05450

DK: Sortklire D: Dunkler Wasserläufer NL: Zwarte Ruiters

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.27.1-4.27.6 Trends of Spotted Redshank in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

The Spotted Redshank is difficult to monitor due to its short passage time period, with large numbers at only a few sites; only some 20% of its flyway population occur in the Wadden Sea. The overall Wadden Sea trend is a moderate decrease in both the long and the short-term, reflected in the Netherlands and Schleswig-Holstein. Trends in Denmark and in Niedersachsen/Hamburg are fluctuating, but resulting in stable trends.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Spotted Redshank in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		→	→
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.27.7 Absolute numbers of Spotted Redshank in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.28 Common Redshank

05460

Tringa totanus

DK: Rødben

D: Rotschenkel

NL: Tureluur

Figure 4.28.1–4.28.6 Trends of Common Redshank in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

The Common Redshank occurs in the Wadden Sea most likely with four populations, thus numbers and trends are not easy to assess in relation to the flyway populations. While the overall Wadden Sea long and short term trends are stable, increasing trends exist the Netherlands and decreasing trend results for Niedersachsen/Hamburg and Schleswig-Holstein.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Redshank in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.28.7 Absolute numbers of Common Redshank in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002–2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 – 2011/12	2002/03 – 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		→	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.29 Common Greenshank

Tringa nebularia

05480

DK: Hvidklire

D: Grünschenkel

NL: Groenpootruiter

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.29.1-4.29.6 Trends of Common Greenshank in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

The Wadden Sea plays a minor role for the Common Greenshanks with only some 10% of the stable flyway population staging during autumn, and fewer during spring. The overall trends in the Wadden Sea are stable, yet fluctuating largely in low numbers. This can be stated also for most regions in the Wadden Sea, only in Schleswig-Holstein both long- and short-term trends show moderate but regular decreases.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Greenshank in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		→	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

Figure 4.29.7 Absolute numbers of Common Greenshank in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.30 Ruddy Turnstone

05610

Arenaria interpres

DK: Stenvender

D: Steinwalzer

NL: Steenloper

Figure 4.30.1–4.30.6 Trends of Ruddy Turnstone in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Two populations of Ruddy Turnstone pass the Wadden Sea on migration. One population, breeds in Canada and Greenland and winters in Western Europe and North-West Africa and is present in the Wadden Sea most of the year from August to April. The other population breeds in Fennoscandia and North-West Russia and winters in Africa, and passes the Wadden Sea mainly during July and May. The overall Wadden Sea trend for this species is stable during both the long- and the short-term trends. Increases, in particular during the recent years, are found mainly in Niedersachsen/Hamburg. Coverage of this species by the Trilateral Monitoring Program is generally poor and low numbers, in particular in Denmark, are registered.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Ruddy Turnstone in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.30.7 Absolute numbers of Ruddy Turnstone in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002–2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 – 2011/12	2002/03 – 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↓	↓↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑	↑
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable ■ uncertain

4.31 Common Black-headed Gull

Larus ridibundus

05820

DK: Hættemåge

D: Lachmöwe

NL: Kokmeeuw

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.31.1-4.31.6 Trends of Common Black-headed Gull in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

The trilateral counts only cover a part of the Black-headed Gull numbers actually using the Wadden Sea, because many birds occur offshore, inland, at harbours or rubbish dumps. For the 20-25 % of the flyway population present in the Wadden Sea the long-term trend is decreasing, the short-term trend stable. This decrease also occurs in Denmark and Niedersachsen/Hamburg. In the Netherlands, where highest numbers occur, strong fluctuations result in stable trends.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Black-headed Gull in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable □ uncertain

Figure 4.31.7 Absolute numbers of Common Black-headed Gull in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.32 Common Gull

05900

Larus canus

DK: Stormmåge

D: Sturmmöwe

NL: Stormmeeuw

Figure 4.32.1-4.32.6 Trends of Common Gull in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Some 10-15% of the Common Gull flyway population use the Wadden Sea, however, many of them feed inland and only rest in the Wadden Sea during night. The overall long- and short-term trends are stable for the Wadden Sea; while numbers fluctuate in all regions, the northern regions (DK, SH) show slight decreases, fluctuations in Niedersachsen/Hamburg and an indication of a positive development in the Netherlands.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Gull in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.32.7 Absolute numbers of Common Gull in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

4.33 Herring Gull

Larus argentatus

05920

DK: Sølvmåge

D: Silbermöwe

NL: Zilvermeeuw

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 4.33.1-4.33.6 Trends of Herring Gull in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Only a small part of the Herring Gull flyway population are registered in the Wadden Sea, however many birds are not covered because birds either feed offshore or inland. The overall trend in the Wadden Sea and all its regions is a clear decrease, with the exception of Denmark, where the population appears to be overall stable.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Herring Gull in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	↓
(C) Denmark		→	→
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↓	↓

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↕ moderate increase
↕ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

Figure 4.33.7 Absolute numbers of Herring Gull in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

4.34 Great Black-backed Gull

06000

Larus marinus

DK: Svartbag D: Mantelmöwe NL: Grote Mantelmeeuw

Figure 4.34.1-4.34.6 Trends of Great Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Only a small fraction of the Great Black-backed Gull flyway population is counted in the Wadden Sea, since many birds use harbours and offshore areas. Apart from some peak numbers in the mid 1990s, most long- and short-term trends in the Wadden Sea and its regions are decreasing.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Great Black-backed Gull in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from all months to express an overall trend for the entire year. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Figure 4.34.7 Absolute numbers of Great Black-backed Gull in the international Wadden Sea and the four regions calculated by average of the 3 maximum numbers in the period 2001/2002-2011/2012.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		↓	↓↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable ■ uncertain

5 Subspecies accounts

Species	Long-term 25-years trend 1987/1988 - 2011/2012						Short-term 10-year trend 2000/2001 - 2011/2012				
	WS	DK	SH	Nds/ HH*	NL		WS	DK	SH	Nds/ HH*	NL
Great Ringed Plover (<i>hiaticula</i>)	→	—	→	↓	↑		→	—	→	↓	—
Great Ringed Plover (<i>psammodroma/tundrae</i>)	↑	—	↑	→	↑↑		↑	—	↑	—	↑
Red Knot (<i>canutus</i>)	→	↑	→	↑	↑		→	↑	↓	↑↑	↑
Red Knot (<i>islandica</i>)	↓	—	↓	→	→		→	—	↓	—	—
Bar-tailed Godwit (<i>taymyrensis</i>)	→	↓	↓	→	↑		→	↓	↓	→	→
Bar-tailed Godwit (<i>lapponica</i>)	→	↓	↓	↓	↑		↓	↓	↓	—	—
Common Redshank (<i>totanus</i>)	↓	→	↓	↓	↑		→	—	↓	↓	↑
Common Redshank (<i>robusta</i>)	→	→	→	↓	→		↓	↓	↓	—	→
Ruddy Turnstone (Greenland & NE Canada)	→	→	→	↑	→		→	↓↓	↓	↑	→
Ruddy Turnstone (Scandi- navia - Western Russia)	→	—	→	→	→		→	↓	→	↑	→

* Data for Niedersachsen/Hamburg was only available up to 2010/2011.

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

WS - Wadden Sea; DK - Denmark; SH - Schleswig-Holstein; Nds/HH - Niedersachsen/Hamburg; NL - The Netherlands

Table 5.1
Trends until 2011/2012 - The whole 25 and last 10 years time period. Data for Nds/HH was only available up to 2010/2011. The species names in the table are sorted according to the Euring Code.

5.1 Common Ringed Plover (*hiaticula*)

04701

Charadrius hiaticula hiaticula

DK: Stor Præstekrave D: Sandregenpfeifer NL: Bontbekplevier

Figure 5.1.1-5.1.6
Trends of subspecies
Great Ringed
Plover (*hiaticula*) in the
international Wadden Sea
(WS) and the four regions
1987/1988-2011/2012; dots
represent annual aver-
ages; trendline calculated
by Trendspotter (solid line)
together with the ± 95 %
confidence limits (dotted
line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Less than 10-20% of the birds passing through belong to the subspecies of *C. h. hiaticula*, the only Ringed Plover being present in late autumn and early spring or even in winter (from October to April). The overall trend seems to be stable, but increasing strongly in the Netherlands, while decreasing in Lower Saxony by the same amount, also decreasing slightly in small numbers in Denmark and keep quite stable in Schleswig-Holstein.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Ringed Plover (*hiaticula*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↑	—

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

5.2 Common Ringed Plover (*psammodroma/tundrae*)*Charadrius hiaticula psammodroma/tundrae*

04702

DK: Stor Præstekrave D: Sandregenpfeifer NL: Bontbekplevier

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 5.2.2-5.2.6 Trends of subspecies Common Ringed Plover (*psammodroma/tundrae*) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the $\pm 95\%$ confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Large numbers of both the arctic breeding *C. h. tundrae* and *C. h. psammodroma* pass through during May and from July to September also. Highest numbers occur in Schleswig-Holstein, half of it in the Netherlands and Lower Saxony and very small numbers in Denmark. Overall results are increasing like in Schleswig-Holstein and the Netherlands, but fluctuating in Lower Saxony and Denmark.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Ringed Plover (*psammodroma/tundrae*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↑	↑
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↑	↑
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	—
(F) The Netherlands		↑↑	↑

↑↑ strong increase ↓↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

5.3 Red Knot (*canutus*)

04961

Calidris canutus canutus

DK: Islandsk Ryle

D: Knutt

NL: Kanoetstrandloper

Figure 5.3.1-5.3.6 Trends of subspecies Red Knot (*canutus*) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Red Knots of the subspecies *C. c. canutus* migrating from Africa to Siberia are mainly present in the Wadden Sea in May and July-August. The overall trend shows a slight increase, although in Schleswig-Holstein with highest numbers a continuous decrease occurs since the late 1990's while numbers are increasing in Denmark and the Netherlands, almost reaching the levels of Schleswig-Holstein in the latest years, but fluctuating in Lower Saxony.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Red Knot (*canutus*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↑	↑
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑	↑↑
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease → stable □ uncertain

5.4 Red Knot (*islandica*)

Calidris canutus islandica

04962

DK: Islandsk Ryle

D: Knutt

NL: Kanoetstrandloper

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 5.4.1-5.4.6 Trends of subspecies Red Knot (*islandica*) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Birds of the subspecies *C. c. islandica* winter in the European region and breed in Greenland and Canada. In opposite to the *C. c. canutus* subspecies the overall trend of *C. c. islandica* shows a strong decrease, mainly in Schleswig-Holstein, but also in the Netherlands, while numbers increase slightly in Denmark and keep stable on very low level in Lower Saxony.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Red Knot (*islandica*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		—	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	—
(F) The Netherlands		→	—

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↕ moderate increase
↕ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

5.5 Bar-tailed Godwit (*taymyrensis*)

05341

Limosa lapponica taymyrensis

DK: Lille Kobbersneppe D: Pfuhschnepfe NL: Rosse Grutto

Figure 5.5.1-5.5.6 Trends of subspecies Bar-tailed Godwit (*taymyrensis*) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Birds of the Siberian subspecies *L. l. taymyrensis* are mainly present in the Wadden Sea in May and in July/August. The overall trend is stable, but different in the sub regions. Most birds occur in the Netherlands, where numbers increased until the mid 1990's and remained stable since then. In opposite a continuous decrease occurred in Schleswig-Holstein and also in Denmark. Numbers remained stable only in Lower Saxony but on much lower level.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Bar-tailed Godwit (*taymyrensis*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		↓	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	→
(F) The Netherlands		↑	→

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

5.6 Bar-tailed Godwit (*lapponica*)

Limosa lapponica lapponica

05342

DK: Lille Kobbersneppe D: Pfuhschnepfe NL: Rosse Grutto

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 5.6.1-5.6.6 Trends of subspecies Bar-tailed Godwit (*lapponica*) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by TrendSpotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Birds of the subspecies *L. l. lapponica* breed in northern Scandinavia and northern Russia and winter in coastal Western Europe and North-West Africa. From September to April all birds in the Wadden Sea are supposed to belong to this subspecies. The overall trend of these wintering birds is fluctuating with decreasing numbers during the last years. Biggest numbers of 20,000 birds in total were recorded each in the Netherlands and Schleswig-Holstein in the late 1980's. While numbers decreased in Schleswig-Holstein continuously by more than 50% like in Denmark and Lower Saxony on much lower level, the opposite happened in the Netherlands by increasing strongly after the mid 1990's, but dropping again during the last years.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Bar-tailed Godwit (*lapponica*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		➡	⬇
(C) Denmark		⬇	⬇
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		⬇	⬇
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		⬇	—
(F) The Netherlands		⬆	—

⬆ strong increase
 ⬇ strong decrease
 ⬆ moderate increase
⬇ moderate decrease
 ➡ stable
 — uncertain

5.7 Common Redshank (*totanus*)

05461

Tringa totanus totanus

DK: Rødben

D: Rotschenkel

NL: Tureluur

Figure 5.7.1–5.7.6 Trends of subspecies Common Redshank (*totanus*) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the ± 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Birds from the Fennoscandia and north-western Russian population *T. t. totanus*, which winter in western Africa, pass through the Wadden Sea in April/May and July/August mainly. The overall trend is stable to slightly decreasing, but very much contrasting within the Wadden Sea regions. Numbers are continuously increasing in the Netherlands and on much lower level in Denmark also, but decreasing strongly in Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Redshank (*totanus*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		↓	→
(C) Denmark		→	—
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		↓	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	↓
(F) The Netherlands		↑	↑

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

5.8 Common Redshank (*robusta*)

Tringa totanus robusta

05462

DK: Rødben

D: Rotschenkel

NL: Tureluur

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 5.8.1-5.8.6 Trends of subspecies Common Redshank (*robusta*) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by TrendSpotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Only birds of the subspecies *T. t. robusta* from islandic breeding grounds winter in the Wadden Sea region. Thus, numbers and trends reflect the occurrence of severe winters. Numbers increased up to the mid 1990's, but dropped rapidly due to the severe winters in the mid 1990's, recovered until 2005/2006 and decreased since then again due to a series of cold winters during the last years. Almost the same pattern appears the same in all regions of the Wadden Sea.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Common Redshank (*robusta*) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	↓
(C) Denmark		→	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↓	—
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

5.9 Ruddy Turnstone (Greenland & NE Canada)

05611

Arenaria interpres morinella

DK: Stenvender

D: Steinwalzer

NL: Steenloper

Figure 5.9.1-5.9.6 Trends of subspecies Ruddy Turnstone (Greenland & NE Canada) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988-2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Explanatory Note

Birds from the Greenlandic and north-eastern Canadian population stay in the Wadden Sea during winter, but also in western Europe and north-western Africa. Like in *Tringa t. robusta* wintering numbers are reflecting the occurrence of severe winters during the last 25 years. Numbers increased after the severe winters in the mid 1980's, dropped again due to the severe winters in the mid 1990's, recovered continuously for several years until 2008 and dropped again during the row of severe winters around 2009-2011. This pattern is most pronounced in the Netherlands and Schleswig-Holstein while numbers are more increasing in Lower Saxony but decreasing in Denmark during last ten years.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Ruddy Turnstone (Greenland & NE Canada) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		→	↓↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	↓
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		↑	↑
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase
 ↓ strong decrease
 ↑ moderate increase
↓ moderate decrease
 → stable
 — uncertain

5.10 Ruddy Turnstone (Scandinavia–Western Russia)

Arenaria interpres

05612

DK: Stenvender

D: Steinwalzer

NL: Steenloper

(A) Overall trend in the international Wadden Sea

(B) Trends in the different countries compared

Figure 5.10.1–5.10.6 Trends of subspecies Ruddy Turnstone (Scandinavia - Western Russia) in the international Wadden Sea (WS) and the four regions 1987/1988–2011/2012; dots represent annual averages; trendline calculated by Trendspotter (solid line) together with the \pm 95 % confidence limits (dotted line).

Explanatory Note

Birds from the Scandinavian and north-western Russian population winter in western Africa and pass the Wadden Sea mainly in May and July. The overall trend is stable with fluctuating numbers. There are small differences within the regions with a slight increase in the Netherlands, a slight decrease in Schleswig-Holstein, a decrease followed by an increase in Lower Saxony and the small numbers in Denmark dropped clearly during the last years.

(C) Denmark

(D) Schleswig-Holstein

(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg

(F) The Netherlands

Trends for Ruddy Turnstone (Scandinavia - Western Russia) in the Wadden Sea

Figures represent the trend 1987/1988 to 2011/2012, taking into account data from those months in which this subspecies dominates counts in the Wadden Sea. Numbers on the y-axis represent monthly mean occurrences. Dots are the individual yearly estimates, solid lines the trend calculated by TrendSpotter, dotted lines the 95% confidence limits of the trend lines.

Area	Period	1987/88 - 2011/12	2002/03 - 2011/12
(A)/(B) International Wadden Sea		→	→
(C) Denmark		—	↓
(D) Schleswig-Holstein		→	→
(E) Niedersachsen/Hamburg		→	↑
(F) The Netherlands		→	→

↑ strong increase ↓ strong decrease ↑ moderate increase
 ↓ moderate decrease → stable — uncertain

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Annex 1 Assignment of species according to living conditions

Table A1.1
Assignment of species
according to food and
feeding habitats

	Food						Feeding habitats				
	shellfish	worms	fish	other vertebrates	plants	omnivorous	salt marsh	tidal	dunes	beach & offshore	coastal grassland
Great Cormorant			x					x			
Eurasian Spoonbill			x					x			
Barnacle Goose					x		x				
Brent Goose					x		x				
Common Shelduck				x				x			
Eurasian Wigeon					x		x				
Common Teal					x		x				
Mallard					x		x				
Northern Pintail					x		x				
Northern Shoveler				x			x				
Common Eider	x							x			
Eurasian Oystercatcher	x							x			
Pied Avocet		x						x			
Common Ringed Plover		x						x			
Kentish Plover		x						x			
European Golden Plover		x									x
Grey Plover		x						x			
Northern Lapwing		x									x
Red Knot	x							x			
Sanderling		x								x	
Curlew Sandpiper		x						x			
Dunlin		x						x			
Ruff		x									x
Bar-tailed Godwit		x						x			
Whimbrel				x				x			
Eurasian Curlew				x				x			
Spotted Redshank			x					x			
Common Redshank				x				x			
Common Greenshank			x					x			
Ruddy Turnstone				x						x	
Black-headed Gull				x				x			
Common Gull				x				x			
European Herring Gull	x							x			
Great Black-backed Gull						x				x	
Total number of species	4	11	4	8	6	1	7	21	0	3	3

Photo:
John Frikke

	Breeding range		Wintering range	
	arctic breeder	non-arctic breeder	Europe	Africa
Great Cormorant		x	x	
Eurasian Spoonbill		x		x
Barnacle Goose	x		x	
Brent Goose	x		x	
Common Shelduck		x	x	
Eurasian Wigeon		x	x	
Common Teal		x	x	
Mallard		x	x	
Northern Pintail		x		x
Northern Shoveler		x	x	
Common Eider		x	x	
Eurasian Oystercatcher		x	x	
Pied Avocet		x	x	
Common Ringed Plover	x			x
Kentish Plover		x	x	
European Golden Plover		x	x	
Grey Plover	x			x
Northern Lapwing		x	x	
Red Knot	x			x
Sanderling	x			x
Curlew Sandpiper	x			x
Dunlin	x		x	
Ruff	x			x
Bar-tailed Godwit	x			x
Whimbrel	x			x
Eurasian Curlew	x		x	
Spotted Redshank		x		x
Common Redshank		x	x	
Common Greenshank		x		x
Ruddy Turnstone	x		x	
Black-headed Gull		x	x	
Common Gull		x	x	
European Herring Gull		x	x	
Great Black-backed Gull		x	x	
Total number of species	13	21	22	12

Table A1.2
Assignment of species
according to breeding and
wintering range.

Annex 2 Counting units in the Wadden Sea

Figure A2.1
The international Wadden Sea, including delimitations of all counting units and spring tide counting sites

Annex 3 Species List

List of the species monitored in the Trilateral Monitoring and Assessment Program (TMAP)

Euring	English name	Scientific name	Dansk navn	Deutscher Name	Nederlandse naam
00720	Great Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	Skarv	Kormoran	Aalscholver
01440	Eurasian Spoonbill	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>	Skestork	Löffler	Lepelaar
01670	Barnacle Goose	<i>Branta leucopsis</i>	Bramgås	Nonnengans	Brandgans
01680	Dark-bellied Brent Goose	<i>Branta bernicla</i>	Knortegås	Ringelgans	Rotgans
01610	Greylag Goose*	<i>Anser anser</i>	Grågås	Graugans	Grauwe Gans
01730	Common shelduck	<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>	Gravand	Brandgans	Bergeend
01790	Eurasian Wigeon	<i>Anas penelope</i>	Pibeand	Pfeifente	Smient
01840	Common Teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Krikand	Krickente	Wintertaling
01860	Mallard	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Gråand	Stockente	Wilde Eend
01890	Northern Pintail	<i>Anas acuta</i>	Spidsand	Spießente	Pijlstaart
01940	Northern Shoveler	<i>Anas clypeata</i>	Skeand	Löffelente	Slobeend
02060	Common Eider	<i>Somateria mollissima</i>	Ederfugl	Eiderente	Eidereend
02430	White-Tailed Eagle*	<i>Haliaeetus albicilla</i>	Havørn	Seeadler	Zeearend
02900	Rough-Legged Buzzard*	<i>Buteo lagopus</i>	Fjeldvåge	Rauhfußbussard	Ruigpootbuizerd
03090	Merlin*	<i>Falco columbarius</i>	Dværgfalk	Merlin	Smelleken
03200	Peregrine Falcon*	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	Vandrefalk	Wanderfalke	Slechtvalk
04500	Eurasian Oystercatcher	<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	Strandskade	Austernfischer	Scholekster
04560	Pied Avocet	<i>Recurvirostra avosetta</i>	Klyde	Säbelschnäbler	Kluut
04700	Common Ringed Plover	<i>Charadrius hiaticula</i>	Stor Præstekrave	Sandregenpfeifer	Bontbekplevier
04770	Kentish Plover	<i>Charadrius alexandrinus</i>	Hvidbrystet Præstekrave	Seeregenpfeifer	Strandplevier
04850	Golden Plover	<i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>	Hjejle; Hedehjejle	Goldregenpfeifer	Goudplevie
04860	Grey Plover	<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>	Strandhjejle	Kiebitzregenpfeifer	Zilverplevier
04930	Northern Lapwing	<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>	Vibe	Kiebitz	Kievit
04960	Red Knot	<i>Calidris canutus</i>	Islandsk Ryle	Knutt	Kanoetstrandloper
04970	Sanderling	<i>Calidris alba</i>	Sandløber	Sanderling	Drieteenstrandloper
05090	Curlew Sandpiper	<i>Calidris ferruginea</i>	Krumnæbbet Ryle	Sichelstrandläufer	Krombekstrandloper
05120	Dunlin	<i>Calidris alpina</i>	Almindelig Ryle	Alpenstrandläufer	Bonte Strandloper
05170	Ruff	<i>Philomachus pugnax</i>	Brushane	Kampfläufer	Kemphaan
05320	Black-tailed Godwit*	<i>Limosa limosa</i>	Stor Kobbersneppe	Uferschnepfe	Grutto
05340	Bar-Tailed Godwit	<i>Limosa lapponica</i>	Lille Kobbersneppe	Pfuhlschnepfe	Rosse Grutto
05380	Whimbrel	<i>Numenius phaeopus</i>	Lille Regnspove	Regenbrachvogel	Regenwulp
05410	Eurasian Curlew	<i>Numenius arquata</i>	Stor Regnspove	Großer Brachvogel	Wulp
05450	Spotted Redshank	<i>Tringa erythropus</i>	Sortklire	Dunkelwasserläufer	Zwarte Ruiter
05460	Common Redshank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	Rødben	Rotschenkel	Tureluur
05480	Common Greenshank	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	Hvidklire	Grünschenkel	Groenpootruiter
05610	Ruddy Turnstone	<i>Arenaria interpres</i>	Stenvender	Steinwälzer	Steenloper
05820	Common Black-headed Gull	<i>Larus ridibundus</i>	Hættemåge	Lachmöwe	Kokmeeuw
05900	Common Gull	<i>Larus canus</i>	Stormmåge	Sturmmöwe	Stormmeeuw
05910	Lesser Black-backed Gull*	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	Sildemåge	Heringsmöwe	Kleine Mantelmeeuw
05920	Herring Gull	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	Sølvmåge	Silbermöwe	Zilvermeeuw
06000	Great Black-backed Gull	<i>Larus marinus</i>	Svartbag	Mantelmöwe	Grote Mantelmeeuw
09780	Shore (Horned) Lark*	<i>Eremophila alpestris</i>	Bjerglærke	Ohrenlerche	Strandleeuwerik
16620	Twite*	<i>Carduelis flavirostris</i>	Bjergirisk	Berghänfling	Frater
18500	Snow Bunting*	<i>Plectrophenax nivalis</i>	Snespurv	Schneeammer	Sneeuwgorst

* Species where data does not allow trend analysis

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